

Southeast Asia. Genetics studies at IRRI have identified several genes for resistance to the Philippine population.

There have been reports of differential reactions of resistant varieties to WBPH populations in South and Southeast Asia. In breeding for WBPH resistance, it is important to select parents that have resistance to local populations. Materials for use in several countries should have resistance to a diversity of WBPH populations.

We determined the response of varieties with different genes for WBPH resistance to help breeders select parent varieties with broad WBPH resistance. IRRI-developed high yielding lines with WBPH resistance also were evaluated in several countries.

The gene sources given in Table 1 were evaluated in six countries using seedbox screening, feeding, and population growth tests. IR2035-117-3 is a resistant check. Its progeny — IR15527-21-2-3, IR15529-253-2-2-2, and IR15795-151-2-3-2-2— showed WBPH resistance in tests throughout South and Southeast Asia.

All gene sources in seedbox evaluation were resistant or moderately resistant at the various locations, except ARC10239 which was susceptible in Vietnam (Table 1). The other varieties were moderately resistant in Vietnam and most were resistant at the other locations.

All resistant varieties significantly reduced WBPH feeding (Table 2). At IRRI and in Indonesia, there was no difference among the resistant cultivars.

The survival test showed fewer WBPH on resistant varieties than on susceptible TN1, except on N22 at IRRI and in Vietnam (Table 3). Although ARC10239 was susceptible in seedbox screening in Vietnam, very few WBPH survived on it.

In population growth tests, all cultivars except N22 at IRRI significantly reduced WBPH populations below those on TN1 (Table 4). Among test cultivars, populations on N22 were generally among the highest. At IRRI, IR2035-117-3 had the lowest population and performed similarly in India, Korea, and Thailand.

Table 3. WBPH survival^a on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Survival (%)					
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Korea Suweon	Thailand		Vietnam Cantho
				Entomology and Zoology Division Bangkok	Thai Rice Research Institute Bangkok	
N22	96 b	40 b	43 b	10 a	66 b	48 bc
ARC10239	68 a	34 b	24 ab	18 a	66 b	14 a
IR2035-117-3	70 a	16 a	20 a	12 a	58 b	—
WC1240	86 ab	40 b	19 a	10 a	42 a	17 a
Colombo	82 ab	44 b	19 a	6 a	58 b	28 ab
TN1	96 b	72 c	60 c	68 b	96 c	70 c

^aAv of 5 replications. Determined at 15 d after inoculation. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Table 4. Population growth^a of WBPH on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Population growth (no./pair)				
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Korea Suweon	Thailand	
				Entomology and Zoology Division Bangkok	Rice Research Institute Bangkok
N22	307 cd	61 b	11 a	8 a	219 c
ARC10239	192 bc	24 a	0 a	11 a	226 c
IR2035-117-3	33 a	17 a	0 a	4 a	163 b
WC1240	126 b	23 a	0 a	4 a	125 a
Colombo	86 b	28 a	0 a	9 a	233 c
TN1	559 d	104 c	202 b	44 b	782 d

^aAv of 5 replications, determined at 30 d after inoculation. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Data show that all the varieties with genes for resistance to the Philippine WBPH population also are resistant or moderately resistant in India, Indonesia, Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam. IR2035-117-3, with *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2*, has been extensively used as parent at IRRI.

Many breeding lines developed from IR2035-117-3 were resistant at all of the locations tested. If differential responses of resistant varieties to WBPH populations throughout Asia are a constraint to breeding, it was not apparent in this study. *☞*

A carbon dioxide-cone (CO₂NE) sampler for arthropods in flooded rice

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We developed a CO₂NE arthropod sampler for obtaining absolute estimates in research plots.

The sampler consists of a portable CO₂ tank with a rubber hose to deliver gas, an aluminum cone, a strainer with an attached plastic vial with a nylon mesh bottom, and an enclosure ring.

The aluminum cone is carefully placed over a rice hill followed by the enclosure ring. The cone is then filled with CO₂ (see photos). A rubber stopper seals off the opening at the top of the cone. After 1-2 min the cone is removed. The arthropods that fell onto the water within the enclosure ring are scooped up with the strainer and collected in the attached vial. Arthropods that fall between tillers are flushed out with water. When sampling is complete, the arthropods in the vial are rinsed out through another vial with 75% alcohol and brought to the laboratory.

The CO₂NE sampler.

Filling the cone with CO₂.

Scooping the arthropods on the water surface.

Arthropod density in three lowland rice varieties determined by FARMCOP and CO₂NE insect samplers,^a IRRI, 1984.

Sampler	Arthropods (no./5 hills on indicated variety)											
	Brown planthopper <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>			Green leafhopper <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.			Green mirid bug <i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>			Wolf spider <i>Lycosa pseudo-annulata</i>		
	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36
FARMCOP	7.2 a	4.0 a	1.6 a	44 a	2.8 a	13.6 a	17.6 a	12.2 a	8.4 a	9.2 a	6.4 a	5.2 a
CO ₂ NE	5.2 a	4.8 a	3.2 a	21 b	4.4 a	15.6 a	22.8 a	17.2 a	13.6 a	9.2 a	8.4 a	7.6 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to t-test (P < 0.01).

The CO₂ NE sampler is inexpensive and easy to handle. A tank containing 22.5 kg of CO₂ costs about \$10 and is enough to sample 2,000 or more hills. In the field, a portable tank with 300 ml of CO₂, can be used to sample 30 to 40

hills.

In a field trial comparing the CO₂NE and a formerly used FARMCOP suction machine, there was almost no difference in the number of arthropods collected (see table).¹

Brown shield bug attack on rice

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A pentatomid or shield bug damaged rice in Dinajpur District, West Bengal, in 1983. Dinajpur is between 25.2° and 26.5°N and 88° and 89° E. Wet season lowland rice is the principal crop, but summer and pre-kharif rice crops are increasing.

Two species of the pentatomid bug were identified by the Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta, as *Dolycoris indicus* Stal and *D. baccarum* Linn (see figure). Nymphs and adults damage rice by sucking plant sap and milk from panicles in dough stage. Panicle sterility averaged 10%. Populations were highest in Apr, when it was not unusual to find 2–3 insects per plant.¹

Rice hispa in Burdwan, West Bengal

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Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* occurs

in only a few areas of West Bengal. In 1984 kharif there was a severe hispa outbreak on 62,341 ha of rice in 5 southern districts.

Data from Burdwan District, which had 24,575 ha attacked by hispa, showed 4 broods during 1984 kharif. The first developed just after